

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.6 IN-HABIT APP (DEMO VERSION)

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	21/12/2022	BOT	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Revisions	22/12/2022	PC, WTG	Final draft, peer reviewed
V 0.3	Final document	31/12/2022	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission

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EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Well-being
KLC	Key Local Contact
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Local Community Activator
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
SMSCs	Small and medium-sized cities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Deliverable description	7
1.2. Inclusion focus	8
1.3. Research focus	8
2. Overview	10
2.1. Introductory process (consortium level)	10
2.2. Production timeline (demo version)	12
2.3. Local adaptations and related communication launch campaigns (test version)	13
3. Design and development (demo version)	14
3.1. Technical functionality, UX and UI	14
3.1.1. Introduction to features	14
3.1.2. Demo characteristics and guide	17
3.2. App database and Data Platform - Interactions	31
3.4. Client level functioning	35
3.5. Server and security features	36
3.6. Visuals	38
4. Next steps	38
4.1. Definition of final missions and local adaptations	38

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4.2. Integration of personal data for research purposes	39
4.3. Testing phase	40
4.4. Gamification actions and conclusions	41
ANNEXES	43
LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES	43

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarises the study and production process of the D 8.6 IN-HABIT APP (demo version), MS8 of the IN-HABIT project. The reported activities were carried out from M5 until M28 of the project, with the cooperation of the WPLs for WP1-4, WP6, WP7.

This document describes the collaborative process involving IN-HABIT's consortium in defining the App main characteristics and purposes, and the following steps taken for the demo implementation involving the technical and management teams from BOT partner.

As for the timing, the demo version of the IN-HABIT APP has already been developed, and is currently under review by the tech team to include specific features to be updated at the beginning of January 2022 and consequently shared among the local PPs for a first launch of the test version in the local contexts.

The final version is intended to be delivered on M36, integrating the work on the data platform and the results of the test phase.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable description

The IN-HABIT APP will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: like a **friendly fellow citizen**. The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role wherever possible (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and communicate the following to them (PUSH):

- content by spatial proximity (user is close to something that interests them and maybe unaware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- content by temporal proximity (an event next week; a discount for something useful);
- communications about activities, or interesting initiatives.

On the other hand, it will allow the user to communicate requests directly to the city administrations, wherever this connection is available, or collect data to share with local administrations for general ameliorations in local contexts (PULL). Also, it will be possible to respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results and data (movement, activities, reading, consultation) on inhabitants' use of the city are delivered - in an anonymous form - to the administrators and to the project research partners for scientific purposes.

The preliminary development was originally due in M22 (June 2022), postponed to M28

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(December 2022) due to the restrictions linked to the COVID pandemic, and a testing period in the cities will follow, up to the delivery of the final version in M36 (August 2023).

1.2. Inclusion focus

The IN-HABIT APP was defined and implemented, in its demo version, considering a variety of target audiences, some of them being less familiar with technologies or digital tools, or having little digital access. These population groups at risk of disadvantage or exclusion are among the core target groups of the project, for these reasons, both the App was imagined and implemented in a user-friendly way and through multiple access modes, allowing even the oldest or less popular devices to access the app (see §2.3); and the launch campaigns will take into account these necessities, and be tailored accordingly depending on the local contexts.

1.3. Research focus

The IN-HABIT-APP is an essential tool for the cities and the IN-HABIT project. Its ability to collect data from citizens very rapidly on a large variety of topics is key for supporting the IN-HABIT research agenda and making cities more inclusive. This constitutes an important and flexible diagnostic tool to assess local issues rapidly. Moreover, the app should allow, wherever possible, direct interactions between citizens and the municipality, not only from a top-down approach, but also in a bottom-up way where citizens can directly report issues to the municipality. This way, the app can also help define and implement local policies.

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As an example, one municipality could be worried about waste collection and the quality of the service provided. Then, a short survey via the app would indicate rapidly where in the city residents are dissatisfied the most with the waste collection service and the reasons being their low satisfaction. Dissatisfaction may arise from the service provided in itself, and the municipality could directly act on that by increasing the number of shifts for instance. If dissatisfaction comes from residents' behaviours, the municipality can provide nudges and use the mission system to induce more virtuous behaviours. Then, by having a follow-up survey after having implemented their policy, cities are also able to assess its effectiveness. In IN-HABIT, the app will provide an opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of their solutions, but it will also help to design nudges to sustain the virtuous behaviours induced by their solutions.

According to the project Grant Agreement, the App will be related also with tasks and activities carried out by other WPs, in particular WP6 and WP7.

The INHABIT-APP will use contents and behavioural studies provided by WP6, and game design assistance from LCREA best-selling game creators. Mobile Experience Sampling will be also enabled for impact assessment purposes on IHW (WP7) as well as behavioural games for co-design and behaviour change actions in WP 5 & 6. People using the app will be geolocalized and will receive prompts asking them to answer short surveys, play or provide other data at different points throughout the day and they will be able to find bonuses or rewards in different locations around the cities. The INHABIT-APP architecture and planning will be flexible and upgradeable, and it will be possible for other cities to adopt it, using their own maps. The app will give users tokens, or rewards, which the city's administrators will be

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able to use as discounts or incentives for using public spaces, transportation, museums, or getting involved in project's initiatives.

2. Overview

2.1. Introductory process (consortium level)

All updates regarding the development of the App have been widely shared with Project Partners (PPs), considering suggestions and possibilities of amelioration whenever possible, through dedicated meetings or in scheduled general meetings, in order to foster inclusion and a collaborative, co-design approach that is key to the project. Research has also been conducted with the city representatives in order to map the already existing apps, locally, to plan potential synergies in the final version.

Discussion on initial technical requirements started with UCO and WTG partners in M5, following meetings with UREAD, ISIM, WTG, UCO, and LCREA partners between M6-M9 to understand in particular:

- The aim of the app;
- Its application in correlation with the KPIs and needs expressed by the cities;
- Its feasibility in relation to the innovation actions undertaken in the cities.

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The main features and interactions of the app were discussed, with the following steps undertaken: providing a list of functionalities for every city to choose from, combining them with missions to accomplish and rewards to be discussed, with the support of the referents for this task from each city; checking the compatibility and the best way to integrate the app with the IN-HABIT platform developed by WTG, in a dashboard, and other technical issues currently being addressed in smaller groups of discussion. Open discussion with relevant partners and participation in meetings with the cities' representatives on the matter has been held and will continue in the following months, with the help of a tailor-made UX guide and user-friendly materials (Annex 1) and several meetings with experts. Current discussion and next steps involve the integration of the IN-HABIT app basic missions structure with the platform developed by WTG and the definition of the rewards with local authorities.

A mockup of the app visuals has been developed and shared during the GAs, and is available on Annex 2. Further updates will be shared during the first Consortium meetings in 2023.

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2.2. Production timeline (demo version)

A visual timeline of the process is available below, detailing all the steps above mentioned in §2.1.

Fig. 1 - Production timeline (demo version)

A list of the ongoing work on the missions definition is available as Annex 3, as a working document.

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2.3. Local adaptations and related communication launch campaigns (test version)

Local versions of the app are currently being programmed and tested, and the missions are being translated by local teams, geo localization of relevant spots are being included. The local adaptations of the demo, in local languages, will be available in M28 - January 2023, in order to be launched locally through a specific communication campaign.

Final local versions will be available after the initial testing phase.

A dedicated meeting among local partners, in particular teams taking care of the communication tasks, has been planned for mid-january 2023, in order to establish the best strategies of engagement for the demo of the app for each context, and personalising the campaign actions depending on the target audiences (see D 8.1. DECO Plan). BOT will coordinate the general campaign in order to maximise dissemination of this tool and will support local teams to do so in their local environments.

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3. Design and development (demo version)

3.1. Technical functionality, UX and UI

3.1.1. Introduction to features

Self assessed missions

Within the IN-HABIT APP the main way to engage with citizens will be to assign them missions. Missions are clear actions, big or small, that support the behavioural nudge in the direction established by a city, in accordance with the project principle. Missions can be done only once or repeated in time to foster the formation of good habits.

In particular, for the demo version, self assessed missions will be available first, with the user confirming to have completed an action and/or a survey, while the implementation of sensors is being carried out to add the device related missions (see below).

For the demo version the following types of mission are available:

GPS: missions that involve reaching a specific location indicated by latitude and longitude coordinates. Once reached, by clicking on the 'Accomplish Mission' button, the system will detect the user's GPS position (specific permissions must be granted to the app; a prompt is shown to ask for permission to use it). If the position is within 2 km in a straight line from the requested position, the mission will be considered completed. If not, an error message will be displayed.

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QR-Code: missions where the user has to search for a certain QR-Code in a specific area of the city indicated on the map. By clicking on the 'Scan QR-Code' button, the system will access the user's rear camera (specific permissions must be granted to the app; a prompt is shown to ask for permission to use it) and will start scanning while waiting to detect a QR-Code. Once detected, it is encoded and sent to the server. The server will check that the particular QR-Code does indeed match the one requested and if so will validate the mission. If not, an error message will be displayed.

Quiz: mission where the user has to correctly answer a number of questions. For the demo, all questions are multiple choice with 1 correct answer. There is no limit to the number of questions to be asked, and there is no limit to the number of wrong answers for each question.

For the final version of the app, other kind of missions will be available, such as multilayer missions in multiple steps (where the user accomplished the mission by answering more than a quiz, for example), or combined missions, where the user is asked to complete a mission by both completing an experience and taking a photo, or such.

Device assessed missions

In the final version, it will be possible to carry out special missions that interact with sensors physically present within the cities. Information on these sensors will be provided by WTG via server-to-server communication and missions will be defined with the support of the project research partners, in particular of WP6 and WP7.

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Triggers

How does a mission get assigned to a citizen? That's what triggers are for. Triggers are the way the app uses to prompt action and are themselves prompted by diverse circumstances. A trigger allows for a message to be sent to the citizen to nudge them to take an action (like going on a mission or sharing a post on social media) based on time of the day, location, proximity to a goal or even in a random way.

Badges, points and rewards

Rewards are the way in which citizens keep score of their good behaviour towards IN-HABIT objectives. A system of badges and points has been developed to show a citizen's achievement towards the behaviours we want to promote and the habits we want to build. Each mission will have a resulting badge or point allocation.

A universal point and badge system is expected and built at the moment, but can be integrated with specific ones from the cities, related to their expertise and geography.

Rewards other than badges (might be discounts on museum entrances, local events and other advantages) have not yet been identified due to complexity of this task, and the many different actors involved in each local community. This task will proceed and be implemented wherever local entities will be cooperative, in the final version of the app.

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3.1.2. Demo characteristics and guide

An IN-HABIT APP demo video, explaining in detail its main features, is available at the following private link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FQ7lGydbghQ> (*subtitles can be activated).

A detailed description follows:

By installing the application or accessing the demo url provided from a mobile phone, the user will have the option of registering again or logging in if already registered.

To complete registration, the user must enter first name, surname, email address, and password, and accept the terms and conditions (obligatory). An email address can register one account only.

For the demo version only, the password is required to contain at least 5 alphanumeric characters. In the final version, the application will only allow complex passwords.

For the demo version only, registration is automatically and immediately validated. In the final version, the application sends an alphanumeric code to the email address provided during registration before validating the user. Registration is only validated once the code received by email has been entered correctly. If the wrong code is entered 5 times in a row, the user account will be deleted.

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Once registered, the user will be automatically logged in. The login session will be kept open until the user deletes cookies (manually or by logging out) or 365 days have passed since the user last logged in.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Sign-Up" on the IN-HABIT platform. The form includes several input fields for registration details, a checkbox for accepting terms and conditions, a "Sign-Up" button, and a link for existing members to "Login". At the bottom, there is a logo for the European Union and text indicating the project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme.

Fig. 2 - Demo version mock-up

If the session is closed, it is possible to log in again via the login page.

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Fig. 3 - Demo version mock up

To log in, simply enter the email address and password chosen during registration. If the data is correct and the user is validated, a new session will be generated which will keep the access valid for a maximum of 365 days via a technical cookie.

When the user logs in, they are redirected to the page that enables them to select one of the four cities where missions can be carried out. The cities are Nitra, Riga, Cordoba and Lucca. Each city is represented by a colour as per the specific graphics provided.

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Fig. 4 - Demo version mock up

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Click on one of the cities to enter that city's page. The page dedicated to each city is marked by a bar at the top in the city's colour, in addition to the name of the city itself. On the left is the IN-HABIT logo. Click on this to go back to the main page to select the city. On the right is a button with three horizontal lines: click on this to open a menu for navigation to specific pages. Under the bar is the city map. In the final version the map will show all the mission locations in graphics.

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Fig. 5 - Demo version mock up

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Missions

Under the map is a list of all the available missions in a given city. The list of missions has 4 pieces of information:

- Mission identification number in a red or green circle. Red if the user has not yet carried out that mission, green if the user has already completed it.
- Icon showing the type of mission (at the moment, the types available are GPS, QR-Code, Quiz).
- Mission name.
- Reward points to be won by carrying out the mission.

Click on an individual mission to access the mission's dedicated page with all the relative information.

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Fig. 6 - Demo version mock up

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In addition to the usual city bar, the mission title and mission description are displayed at the top. The mission description explains in detail how to complete the mission.

If the mission involves reaching a specific location, a map of that specific location is also included.

Finally, some details of the mission's progress are offered, including any technical information, score, and award badges in case the mission is completed.

In particular, each mission can bestow a certain number of points and a certain badge. Badges are graphic awards that the user can find on their profile after earning them.

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Click on the Menu key to show the following menu:

Fig. 7 - Demo version mock up

The menu is the same colour as the city in which it is opened. In the demo version, the items on the menu are:

- **User name and Points:** non-clickable item showing only the user's name and accumulated points.
- **Badges:** clickable item that takes the user to their badge collection.
- **City:** clickable item that takes the user to the city selection page.

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- **Logout:** clickable item that enables the user to stop the session, cancel cookies, and return to the login page.

Completing missions

By accessing the Badges page, the user will find a graphic list of all existing badges. Those earned will be coloured, while those not yet unlocked will be grayscaled and semi-transparent. In the final version, it will be possible to click on each badge and see immediately which missions allow the user to earn that badge on completion.

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Fig. 8 - Demo version mock up

Badges will be the same for all cities, and matching related missions. Badges identified so far include:

- Brave Badge

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- Jogger Badge
- Advance Jogger Badge
- Explorer Badge
- You Know Them All! Bagde
- Improve your city Badge
- Friend Finder Badge
- IN-HABIT lover badge
- Good citizen Badge
- Animal Lover Badge
- Nature Lover Badge
- Participant Badge
- Healthy Badge
- Advanced Healthy Badge
- Green Badge
- Culture Lover Badge
- Art Lover badge

Device assessed missions (sensors)

As above mentioned, special missions involving sensors installed locally will be included in the final version of the App, since sensor installation is currently ongoing on the field by WTG. The following diagram shows the communication scheme between the platforms and the end users. WTG will only be queried by the application server, which will then communicate bi-directionally with individual users via the client application.

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Fig. 9 - Communication flow server/platform/clients

Partner WTG has been conducting research, both online and offline, on the field, to understand and verify what kind of sensors might be installed in each city. The data deriving from these sensors will feed the app in its final version through an integration dynamic described in § 3.2.

So far, no existing database has been detected in the cities involved in the project by WTG, while a list of possible sensors to be installed would include the following information, for example in the case of Córdoba: there are 24 “patios”, in which one are going to be installed the following sensors: 1x PAR radiation; 2x Air temperature, humidity and CO2 level; 1x Soil temperature, moisture and electrical conductivity; 1x Water flowmeter.

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Regarding the other cities, the available information so far points at the following probable sensors installation (installation scope highlights):

- Cordoba: measuring temperature, moisture and electrical conductivity of the soil; temperature, humidity and CO2 level of the air; water-meter; and PAR radiation. There will be some sensors at each “patio”.
- Lucca: installing some video cameras to count people and pets going in/out on specific parks, and waste fill level sensors in the bins installed at these parks.
- Nitra: people flow monitoring at some spaces designated to social activities and bike lanes; or measuring environment parameters with a weather station in a meeting area.
- Riga: installing sensors in a market to measure some air parameters (temperature, humidity and CO2) and counting people who come in/out the market with embed video analytics in cameras.

These sensors will be related to specific missions as mentioned above. The process of sensor research and development will be described in detail in further documentation by partner WTG, due on M32.

3.2. App database and Data Platform - Interactions

The IN-HABIT APP and the Data Platform will be interconnected, according to the following simplified scheme:

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(T 8.2, D 8.6) IN-HABIT APP - app data flow (simplified version)

Fig. 10 - Integration APP/Platform general scheme

IN-HABIT data platform is a FIWARE-based platform designed and created by WELLNESS TECH GROUP following the requirements of the IN- HABIT project. The platform will collect information from several sources (devices, sensors, cameras, app...) and will show the information in a GRAFANA-based dashboard, and through API (T 7.2).

Developed and managed by partner WTG, it will be a long-term sustainable data platform securing open and consistent data about the performance and impacts of the deployed solutions in the four IN-HABIT cities. The IN-HABIT platform will be used for co-design and monitoring purposes in WPs 1-4, to collect data in WP5 and WP6, for impact assessment purposes in WP7 and for communication and dissemination activities in WP8, in particular in connection with the IN-HABIT APP. The platform will allow for the integration, management

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and visualisations of data from various sources (sensors, cameras, open data, mobile app) at city level (i.e., air pollution and temperature, movements of persons and vehicles, noise, landscape features), to produce interactive scenarios, GIS mapping and spatial/environmental analysis in real time. It will be operational at M32.

A more comprehensive description of the platform can be found on Annex 4.

Technical integration of the app and dashboard collecting data (platform) is currently ongoing, according to the following steps:

- A manual for the integration has been written and sent by BOT on M25 (Annex 5);
- A document proposing possible technical solutions of integration has been shared by WTG in M28 (Annex 6);
- Technical meetings towards the integration will follow from M29 on, in order to agree on the work plan for the final app version.

Generally speaking, the interchange of data will work both ways:

- BOT to WTG: BOT provides an API which can be used by WTG to get information generated by the citizens using the mobile app and show it in the dashboard. WTG will develop a scheduled process (cronjob) in the backend service to get the KPIs generated by BOT;
- WTG to BOT: probably use of a subscription service to send the information generated by the sensors in real-time to BOT software. When the platform receives a new data from the acquisition layer, it notifies to a configured http endpoint sending that data.

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The KPI data model template which allows both parties to define which data to be collect from BOT API and show it in WTG dashboard is still to be confirmed.

More information about this integration process will be available in the next weeks and towards D 8.8 IN-HABIT APP final version (M36).

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3.4. Client level functioning

The demo is available in 3 possible versions:

Native application (APK installable in debug version) usable only on Android devices. In order to install this version, the tester must authorise the installation of non-certified apps (as they are still under development).

Web App directly from mobile browser by accessing the web address supplied.

Progressive Web App (PWA): app generated on the fly directly via mobile browser. Once generated the login icon will appear directly on the user's smartphone.

In case of installation of the native app via APK, permissions (to use the camera and GPS) will be requested during the first use. In case of access via browser, permissions will only be requested when it is actually necessary to access the location or the camera. Beyond the application wrapper, the technology is still web-based according to the HTML5 standard. In addition to HTML5, CSS and JavaScript are used.

This technology makes it possible to have the app always running via mobile browser regardless of whether or not it is in the App Stores (Google Play and Apple Store).

All updates will be via server, and users will always have the latest version of the product without having to manually download any updates.

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3.5. Server and security features

The server application runs on a customised Linux cloud environment of which our technical staff has full remote control. The operating system installed is Centos 7.9. The cloud runs on real machines in an ISO 27001-certified data centre in Germany.

Access to the virtual machines for the project takes place via an SSH connection on a non-default port, by means of a dedicated key or highly complex passwords (minimum 40 characters in total, multiple special characters, multiple uppercase letters, multiple lowercase letters, multiple numbers). Access passwords are only stored on specific devices in an encrypted manner. Passwords are not shared digitally and are physically available exclusively to management personnel.

The server software is written in PHP 7 and its performance is optimised through the use of the OPcache module. The Web server is Apache 2.4. The database is MySQL and specifically MariaDB 10.4.

All user passwords are stored in the database solely in the international SHA-2 (Secure Hash Algorithm) encryption format developed by the US NSA. The encryption is irreversible and does not allow users' real passwords to be traced.

The virtual machines are also protected against DDOS attacks at both software and hardware level. At the hardware level, protection is provided directly by the server farm, while at the software level, the specially configured Apache Evasive module is used. To guarantee greater protection against hacking attempts we also use Fail2Ban software.

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All software is updated weekly to ensure that the latest versions and security patches are always present.

As far as user data is concerned, at this stage, the only personal data we keep are first name, last name and email. Passwords are irreversibly encrypted (it is not technically possible to reconstruct the password from the stored hash). All other data is of a technical nature for app function. For example, the IDs of missions carried out, or the IDs of unlocked badges. No GPS positions or anything else are stored at the moment. The whole system runs on the cloud according to the strictest security standards. The use of firewalls and other specific software to guarantee data security.

For missions where data (i.e. a photo) needs to be uploaded, storage will be taken care of by BOT and its technical team, in a safe database. This information is not currently present in the prototype and has not yet been defined, but it has in general been defined as an availability of a database storing about 40.000 contacts for each city. This possibility was communicated in M27 to PC and WTG partner, in order to better support the App and the integration with the platform, and to meet the D 9.2. Data Management Plan requirements.

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3.6. Visuals

The IN-HABIT APP is being developed according to the project visual guidelines and assets, available in the D 8.1. Deco Plan (Visual identity guidelines).

4. Next steps

4.1. Definition of final missions and local adaptations

Concerning missions, they will be enhanced based on the test feedback. In addition, work around multiple-step missions has been planned. In particular missions which can be envisaged as extra possibilities on top of those designed are:

Missions with multiple GPS points: the user will have to check in at multiple GPS points to complete the mission. Preferably avoiding the time base (within 24 hours, within 12 hours, etc.) to lighten the amount of data to be stored on the app.

Missions with multiple QR Codes: the user will have to scan multiple QR Codes to complete the mission.

At the moment, missions are being reviewed by research partners in order to guarantee a user-friendly access and engagement, and will be updated in M28, before launching the test in the cities.

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4.2. Integration of personal data for research purposes

In view of the possible outcomes regarding research and scientific publications deriving from data collection, an analysis has been put in place regarding the feasibility of exploring the population of users through detailed surveys. Excluding long and detailed surveys through the app, not considered feasible due to both sensitive information and engagement issues, two data categories were identified:

1. must-have category, in particular: age, gender, georeferencing, a unique user ID to track people over time, a set of self-assessment health measures (at least physical and mental, still to be defined how many measurements for each), and a set of self-assessment well being measures (mental health can actually work for wellbeing but maybe at least one other that captures a different dimension might be good).
2. Nice-to-have, in particular other diversity dimensions such as ethnic group, disability status, income level (could be in terms of self-assessment, or brackets), sexual identity, and religious group. It is yet to be considered whether it is worth adding some other socio-demographics like education level and employment status.

Beyond these two categories, through the app the project will collect more specific surveys depending on the current research agenda of each WP and the work carried out specifically, Namely, it might concern short modules on discrimination, experience of the urban space, transportation system, interactions with the public authorities, local institutions and so forth.

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4.3. Testing phase

The testing phase will be carried out in Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga from M29 to M36, when the final version of the app will be available. In the meantime, the demo version will be shared with local communities or working groups to be identified together with the local IN-HUBS participants, and its use promoted through a communication plan.

The testing phase will allow to evaluate the feasibility of the missions, the degrees of success of them, the degree of engagement of the population, and so forth. During the testing phase, multiple technical tests will be implemented to make sure that the final version of the IN-HABIT APP can run smoothly.

During this phase, KPIs for the app's correct functioning could be identified among PPs, in order to be traced from M37 on.

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4.4. Gamification actions and conclusions

The gamification actions of the app will take into account T 6.4 (Behavioural games to boost changes), consisting in the implementation of behavioural games aimed at proposing behavioural alternatives that may contribute to change the personal way of thinking, acting and relating to others in the daily life, with a focus on women and other vulnerable target groups (elderly, persons with disability, persons with a migrant background). The games will focus on behaviours that boost IHW with a focus on culture, food, human bonds and the environment. They will be particularly aimed at reducing gaps in the self-determination, autonomy, social inclusion, use and ownership of the public space, awareness, self-esteem, access to and use of social power, encouraging active participation and citizenship.

The app will promote these goals empowering nudging and engagement of the participants. Depending on the specific city case, these games will be adapted to the local specific objectives regarding IHW, by sustaining behavioural changes on healthy lifestyles like healthy diets, sustainable mobility (walking and cycling), socialisation and cultural habits among both local citizens and tourists.

Behavioural games, facilitated by UREAD, will be digitally enhanced by means of digital gamification techniques developed by partners LCREA & BOT and distributed on mobile devices through the INHABIT-APP, to be implemented at wide scale as digital games. Community activators will be key in implementing this via broad promotion of the IN- HABIT APP and by delivering workshops with key stakeholders.

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Wording and UX will be ameliorated to make the user experience pleasant, interesting and engaging.

The final delivery of the App in M36, will collect the feedback from the text phase and include it, along with implementation of the missions deriving from the devices installed locally by PP WTG (WP7) and the final integration of the APP with the Data Platform under development at the moment. In view of the final version, careful checks and verifications will be carried out with the research Project Partners in particular, in order to calibrate the App on the desired aims in terms of data collection for the project research.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 - Annex 1_WP8_IN-HABIT APP UX presentation

Annex 2 - Annex 2_ WP8_IN-HABIT APP example mock ups

Annex 3 - Annex 3_WP8 BOT_IN-HABIT APP BASIC STRUCTURE

Annex 4 - Annex 3_WTG_IN HABIT PLATFORM_general info

Annex 5 - Annex 4_ WP8_ExternalAPI_v_1.0_BOT

Annex 6 - Annex 5_WTG_BOT Integration 20221202

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Table/Fig. no.	Content	Page
<i>Fig. 1</i>	<i>Fig. 1 - Production timeline (demo version)</i>	13
<i>Figg. 2 - 8</i>	<i>Fig. 2 - 8 - Demo visual mockups</i>	18 to 28
<i>Fig. 9</i>	<i>Fig. 9 - Communication flow server/platform/clients</i>	30
<i>Fig. 10</i>	<i>Fig. 10 - Integration APP/Platform general scheme</i>	32

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The logo features a central white circle containing the text 'IN-HABIT' in a bold, white, sans-serif font. The 'IN' is positioned inside the circle, while '-HABIT' extends to the right. Four white lines radiate from the central circle to four smaller white circles, one in each quadrant (top-left, top-right, bottom-left, bottom-right).

IN-HABIT

D 8.6 IN-HABIT APP

01/06/2022

UX guidance

Book on a Tree – WP8

IN-HABIT APP - a fellow citizen

The APP will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: it's like a friendly fellow citizen.

The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and at this point communicate the following with them (PUSH)

- a) content by spatial proximity** (you're close to something that interests you and maybe you're not aware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- b) content by temporal proximity** (an event next week; a discount for something useful);
- c) communications about activities, discounts, offers** you're entitled to.

On the other hand, **it allows the user to communicate requests, to the city referents** (PULL), and respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results, and data (movement, activities, reading, consultations) on citizens' use of the city.

WHAT IS A MISSION?

Within the In-Habit app the main way to engage with citizens will be assign them missions. **Missions are clear actions, big or small, that support the behavioural nudge in the direction established by a city, in accordance with the In-Habit principle.**

Missions can be done only once or repeated in time to foster the formation of good habits.

An example of mission could be:

- One that confirms a positive habit like: Make sure you have recycled this week and put out your recycling on the right day for collection
- or one connected with a specific location like: Walk the dog to a specific pet dedicated park
- One that involves other individuals: Engage with someone from a specific community to foster knowledge exchange with a diverse community (for example a senior citizen)
- Attend a specific event: Attend the book presentation at this address

Most missions will use 2 main data sources: geolocation and self-certification ("I confirm I did this") like most health and fitness apps do (just to cite an example of app we use every day). Additional data sources, like specific sensors in the city, will be developed later on in collaboration with the city representatives.

WHAT IS A TRIGGER?

How does a mission get assigned to a citizen? That's what triggers are for.

Triggers are the way the app uses to prompt action and are themselves prompted by diverse circumstances.

A trigger allows for a message to be sent to the citizen to nudge them to take an action (like going on a mission or sharing a post on social media) based on time of the day, location, proximity to a goal or even in a random way.

Let's look at some examples for each:

- "It's 6 pm, remember to bring out recycling for collection today"
- "You are near the Washington Square park! Discover more about its history by reading the plaque under the statue"
- "You've completed 7 out of 8 quizzes about the city of Riga sustainable development program, why not take the last one to get a badge?"
- "You haven't shared some In-Habit news in a while? Have a read in our news section and see if there's something worth sharing with your family and friends!"

WHAT IS A REWARD?

Rewards are the way in which citizens keep score of their good behaviour towards In-Habit objectives.

We will develop a system of badges and/or points to show a citizens achievement towards the behaviours we want to promote and the habits we want to build.

Each mission will have a resulting badge or point allocation.

For example:

- You've walked your dog in a designed area for pets 7 days in a row! You get the Bronze badge for best dog walker! Keep it up!
- You have shared In-Habit news on social media for the 20th time! You get a silver badge for social sharing!

A great way to see how a badge and point system works is on apps like Audible and Google Maps (see screenshots below).

We expect to have a universal point and badge system but also to have each city come up with their specific ones, related to their expertise and geography.

Thank you!

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Home Page

Login Page

Sign Up Page

Sign Up Page Final Step

In-Habit

Sign Up

We have sent a code to your inbox. Enter it to validate your account.

Code

Confirm

City Page

Each point on the map will have a different icon depending on the type of mission to be performed.

GEO Mission Page

QR Code Mission Page

Quiz Mission Page

Survey Mission Page

Upload Mission Page

Mission Accomplished Page

User Profile Page

Awards Page

Award Page

City News Page

City Feedback Page

No.	CITY	MISSION'S NAME	MISSION'S DESCRIPTION	POINTS	BADGE	REWARD	TRIGGER	TIMING	NOTES	PLATFORM - MUST HAVE INFO
1	Lucca	Be brave!	Are you ready to discover the Animal Lines around the city? Be brave enough	300	Brave Badge	NO	geolocalization	One Shot		Has the action been performed? (if not, show how many locations
2	Lucca	Roaming around the Animal Lines	Walking or running on the Animal Lines with or without the pet for almost 5	200	Jogger Badge	NO	geolocalization	Always On		Has the action been performed?; time and location of start and finish
3	Lucca	Completing the Animal Lines path	Walking or running with or without the pet covering the whole route of the	500	Advance Jogger Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been performed?; time and location of start and finish
4	Lucca	Let's visit an IN-HABIT's area	Visiting with regularity or for the first time a dog walking area created with	400	Explorer Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been performed?; How many times it has been
5	Lucca	Quiz time!	Quiz. Notification: Do you have 10 minutes for us?	200	You Know Them All! Badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the quiz been completed?; time and location of start and finish of
6	Lucca	Questionaire time!	Questionaire on the benefits brought by the project IN-HABIT, other	300	Improve your city Badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; How many times has the action
7	Lucca	Let's Socialize!	make some new friends during a walk or a visit in the IN-HABIT areas	200	Friend Finder Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
8	Lucca	Event	Participation in an IN-HABIT event	500	IN-HABIT lover badge	NO	qr code	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
9	Lucca	Good practices	Use of the baskets for animal's waists- Report good practices that can be	100	Good citizen Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and
10	Lucca	Let's go to the Kennel!	Becoming a volunteer at the kennel. Or visit the kennel. Take the dogs from	600	Animal Lover Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
11	Lucca	Special Bonus	Report wildlife and tree species spotted along the Animal lines	200	Nature Lover Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; If more than once action has been
12	ISIM for Lucca n.1	What's your feeling?	Have you visited the Animabili Areas around the city? Tell us a little more	200	Explorer Badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Has the action been completed?; Has a comment been left?; time and
13	ISIM for Lucca n.2	What's your feeling?	Have you participated in today's ecowalk/event? Tell us a little more about	300	Participant Badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; Has a comment been left?; time
14	ISIM for Lucca n.3	Healthy life with IN-HABIT	Try at least twice one of the human-animal sports missions and then answer	300	Participant badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Have you tried the product?; Have you tried the product twice?; time
15	ISIM for Lucca n.4	Proud to be from Lucca with IN-HABIT	Do you live in Lucca? Take a picture of a place, an event or something else	400	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the photo been taken?; has the quiz been answered?; time and
16	Riga	Positive habits (For healthy and	Eat more vegetables and fruits. (Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits a day)	100	Healthy Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
17	Riga	Positive habits (For healthy and	No eating between meals.	100	Healthy Badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
18	Riga	Positive habits (For healthy and	Replace unhealthy products with healthier ones (with less sugar, salt, fat,	200	Advanced Healthy Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
19	Riga	Positive habits (On the reduction of	Use leftover food, freezing it, use it in new dishes, share food with others, buy	300	Green Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
20	Riga	Site visit	Visit Agenskalns market	200	Explorer Badge	NO	geolocalization	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
21	Riga	Contribute to the local community (as	Take an active role in master classes organised by Agenskalns market	300	Participant badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
22	Riga	Contribute to the local community (as	Sell homemade products, organize master class, participate in social events for	400	Participant badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
23	ISIM for Riga n.1	What's your feeling?	Have you visited the community kitchen in Agenskalns Market? Tell us a little	300	Participant badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
24	ISIM for Riga n.2	What's your feeling?	Have you participated in today's workshop/event? Tell us a little more about	300	Participant badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
25	ISIM for Riga n.3	Healthy week with IN-HABIT	Try at least two of the "Positive Habits" missions in a week and then answer	500	Advanced healthy badge	NO	qr code	Always On		Have at least two of the missions happened in the space of a week?;
26	ISIM for Riga n.4	Proud to be from Agenskalns with IN-HABIT	Do you live in Agenskalns? Take a picture of a place, an event or something else created by IN-HABIT in the neighbourhood that makes you feel proud to	400	Good citizen Badge	NO	qr code	Always On		time and location of start and finish of each action; user data
27	Cordoba	We are what we eat	Eat products that are good for your health and for the environment! The user has to prepare a meal with in-season and local products	100	Healthy Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
28	Cordoba	Discovering pleasant routes	Keep your body moving!	100	Explorer Badge	NO	geolocalization	Always On		of the action; user data (gender, age, ethnicity)
29	Cordoba	What do you know about the INHABIT	"Complete the inhabit questionnaire"	200	Participant badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; How long the action was (to match
30	Cordoba	Nature's lover	"Go to green areas in your neighbourhood/city and name at least 5 different	200	Explorer Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the questionnaire been completed?; % of completion, time and
31	Cordoba	Know your heritage I	"Identify three monuments that are from different centuries/era"	200	Explorer Badge	NO	update contents	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; % of completion, time and location
32	Cordoba	Know your heritage II	"Identify the place and period to which this monument belongs"	200	You Know Them All! Badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
33	Cordoba	Action for environmental sustainability	"Recycle an unwanted object for another use"	300	Green Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
34	Cordoba	What's going on in the city?	"Go to a free cultural event"	400	Culture Lover Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
35	Cordoba	Discovering pleasant spots	Find an area where you can enjoy nature and art at the same time.	400	Art Lover badge	NO	geolocalization	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
36	Cordoba	Serving others	"Do volunteer work for your community"	500	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish
37	ISIM for Cordoba n.1	What's your feeling?	Have you visited the renovated patios and squares in Palmeras? Tell us a little	300	Participant badge	NO	quiz	Always On		Has the action been completed?; Has text/comment been added?;
38	ISIM for Cordoba n.2	What's your feeling?	Have you participated in today's workshop/event? Tell us a little more about	300	Participant badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		Has the action been completed?; Has text/comment been added?;
39	ISIM for Cordoba n.3	Healthy life with IN-HABIT	Do you live in Palmeras? Try at least two of the healthy missions and then answer to our health quiz. You can choose to try two activities among: "We are what we eat", "Discovering pleasant routes", "Discovering pleasant spots"	500	Advanced healthy badge	NO	quiz	Always On		published after at least two healthy habits missions in Cordoba (with the related missions still available)
40	ISIM for Cordoba n.4	Proud to be from Palmeras with IN-HABIT	Do you live in Palmeras? Take a picture of a place, an event or something else created by IN-HABIT in the neighbourhood that makes you feel proud to be from here. Upload the picture and answer to the short quiz below.	400	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; Has the quiz been completed?; time and location of start and finish of the action; user data (gender, age, ethnicity)
41	Nitra	Change your diet	Share with us a photo of your favorite healthy meal that you cooked at home	100	Healthy Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the photo been taken?; Has the recipe being added?; time and
42	Nitra	Help as a volunteer	Try volunteering for one day in any organization based in our city or at the IN-HABIT project and share your experience.	500	Participant badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish of the action; user data (gender, age, ethnicity)
43	Nitra	Improve your neighborhood	Pay attention and care for the environment in your neighborhood / on your street. Plant greenery, maintain greenery, collect trash, or in any way help the environment in your neighborhood and share your results.	300	Green Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; time and location of start and finish of the action; user data (gender, age, ethnicity)
44	Nitra	Explore the corridor Zelokvet - Mestský	Explore the corridor (cycling route) Zelokvet - City Park - Drážovce as a	400	Explorer Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		Has the action been completed?; Has the photo been updated?; time
45	Nitra	Discover interesting places	Play the geocaching game with us and find 8 QR codes with descriptions of interesting places on the route Zelokvet - Mestský park - Drážovce. Can you find all 8? The reward will be interesting information about the place given on a small information board.	500	Explorer Badge	NO	qr code	One Shot		If possible, include photo of the corridor in the mission description
46	Nitra	Recognize art in public space	There is art all around us in public space - art can be anything from an object or sculpture to wood gnawed by a river beaver. Capture with your camera anything you consider to be art on the Zelokvet - Mestský park - Drážovce. Visit cultural events in the city and earn points for participation. Enjoy the culture in Nitra and upload a photo of your experience from any event.	300	Art Lover badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo. If possible, include photo of the corridor in the mission description
47	Nitra	Enjoy the variety of cultural events in the city	Visit cultural events in the city and earn points for participation. Enjoy the culture in Nitra and upload a photo of your experience from any event.	300	Culture Lover Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
48	Nitra	Organize an activity for at least 5 other	Organize an activity in a public space together with at least 5 other people	500	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
49	Nitra	Make cultural experience accessible	Provide access to cultural experiences to someone (grandparent, disabled	400	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
50	Nitra	How do you use public space?	Fill out a short questionnaire and get points. Where, how and with whom do	200	Participant badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		closed-ended questionnaire with multiple response
51	ISIM for Nitra n.1	What's your feeling?	Have you visited the renovated spaces along the bike route? Tell us a little	200	Participant badge	NO	quiz	Always On		closed-ended questionnaire with multiple response
52	ISIM for Nitra n.2	What's your feeling?	Have you participated in today's workshop/event? Tell us a little more about	200	Participant badge	NO	quiz	One Shot		closed-ended questionnaire with multiple response
53	ISIM for Nitra n.3	Healthy week with IN-HABIT	Try at least two of the Healthy Life missions in a week and then answer to our	500	Advanced healthy badge	NO	quiz	Always On		published after at least two healthy life missions in
54	ISIM for Nitra n.4	Proud to be from Nitra with IN-HABIT	Do you live in Nitra? Take a picture of a place, an event or something else	400	Good citizen Badge	NO	quiz	Always On		upload photo + quiz
55	UREAD for all cities	Treasure hunt	Treasure hunt for a monument depicting a key dimension of diversity the	100	Explorer Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
56	UREAD for all cities	Memory lane	Check all the streets you find that are dedicated to women (more points for	200	Explorer Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
57	UREAD for all cities	Celebration quest	Find the number of statues in the city; how many are of men? How many are	200	You Know Them All! Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		geolocalization + photo
58	UREAD for all cities	Tracking mobility 1	Task: go from point A to B in the city on foot or on a wheelchair (for Lucca	400	Green Badge	NO	quiz	Always On		geolocalization + quiz
60	UREAD for all cities	Tracking mobility 2	count transports available next to your school?	200	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		photo
60	UREAD for all cities	Tracking mobility 2	Count transports available next to your school?	200	Good citizen Badge	NO	update contents	Always On		photo

IN-HABIT

External API Integration Guidelines

V. 1.0

Index

1. Introduction
2. Firewall
3. API output format
4. API list

1 – Introduction

The aim of this document is to provide the specifications to integrate with our APP Server platform. To obtain data and information, our platform exposes a series of APIs which will be described in this document.

The expected integration model is a Server To Server model through HTTPS calls.

This is a diagram that represents the system architecture:

IN-HABIT

2 – Firewall

Our API system is not based on a password authentication system, but on automatic authentication via IP. To be able to integrate with our system the first thing the partner must do is to provide us with the IP addresses (both production and test) of the servers that will make the calls to our platform. These IP addresses will be whitelisted by our firewall and will then be able to make calls.

When your IP addresses are whitelisted, you will receive by email the host for API calls. This document generally indicates the [apihost] variable in place of the real API host.

3 – API Output Format

If evoked by an IP present in our whitelist, all the APIs respond in json format. Otherwise a 404 error will be returned.

4 – API List

4.1 – Connection Test

Purpose: Test the correct integration with the platform.

Endpoint: [https://\[apihost\]/api/1.0/connection-test/](https://[apihost]/api/1.0/connection-test/)

Response:

Parameter Name	Parameter Type	Parameter Description
status	string	“ok” if connection test succeeded

4.2 – List of the cities

Purpose: This API returns the list of all the cities participating in the project with their IDs. It is recommended that you use this API to save unique city IDs to your database for use in other APIs.

Endpoint: [https://\[apihost\]/api/1.0/get-cities/](https://[apihost]/api/1.0/get-cities/)

Response:

Parameter Name	Parameter Type	Parameter Description
status	string	“ok” or “error”
cities	array	Array of individual cities

City Object Format:

Parameter Name	Parameter Type	Parameter Description
id	int	The unique id of the city
name	string	The name of the city
lastupdate	int	Unix timestamp of the last activity concerning the city

4.3 – City statistics

Purpose: This API returns the statistics of a specific city identified by its unique id.

Endpoint: [https://\[apihost\]/api/1.0/get-city-stat/\[cityid\]/](https://[apihost]/api/1.0/get-city-stat/[cityid]/)

Response:

Parameter Name	Parameter Type	Parameter Description
status	string	“ok” or “error”
name	string	The name of the city
lastupdate	int	Unix timestamp of the last activity concerning the city
nusers	int	Total number of app users who have been active in the city since the launch of the app
nmissions	int	Number of missions entered in the database for the city
ncmissions	int	Total number of completed missions in the city since the launch of the app
nuploads	int	Total number of uploads sent by users in the city since the launch of the app
nfeedback	int	Total number of feedback sent by users in the city since the launch of the app

nnews	int	Total number of news concerning the city published by the managers
nawards	int	Total number of rewards won by users in the city since the launch of the app

BOT App – WTG Platform integration

IN-HABIT 02.12.2022

BOT Software (estimated)

- Database for data storage of the application
- Backend to process all the information generated by the users and gathered from third-party platforms
- Integration interfaces:
 - API restful to allow the extraction of data from third-parties
 - Subscription endpoint to manage the received information through this method
 - Requesting service to connect to a third-party API service
- Frontend: There are two different applications, a mobile app and a web app. The users will be the citizens who are participating in the proposals activities

WTG Platform (standard Fiware based, UNE178104)

- Sensors layer: Different sensors can send to the platform using LoraWAN, 3G / 4G or Sigfox protocols
- Acquisition layer: Allow the connections of the sensors with the platform, using a broker which accept several protocols (MQTT, CoAP and HTTP) and a ETL software (Extraction, Transformation, Load) to parse the frame to inject the data into the platform
- Persistence layer: The core service is Orion Context Broker (OCB) which acts as a data exchanger, sending the last data to a NoSQL DB and storing it into the SQL DB for long-term purpose. Also we have in this layer the integration interfaces to connect with third-party software
- Presentation layer: We are developing a dashboard to show the processed data and KPIs. The users will be the city managers and universities

BOT → WTG

- BOT provides an API which can be used by WTG to get information generated by the citizens using the mobile app and show it in the dashboard. We will develop a scheduled process (cronjob) in the backend service to get the KPIs generated by BOT

WTG → BOT

- Our proposal is to use a subscription service to send the information generated by the sensors in real-time to BOT software. When the platform receives a new data from the acquisition layer, it notifies to a configured http endpoint sending that data.

Fiware Subscriptions

https://fiware-orion.readthedocs.io/en/latest/user/walkthrough_apiv2.html#subscriptions

Fiware Notifications

<https://fiware-orion.readthedocs.io/en/latest/orion-api.html#notification-messages>

Basically, we can configure OCB to send a HTTP POST asynchronous notification to an endpoint when something happens (for example a new data from a sensor). The endpoint receives a notification with two fields:

- subscriptionID: To identify it (the same endpoint can manage several subscriptions)
- data: is an array with the notification data itself which includes the entity and all concerned attributes

Subscription example

The data model of a sensor, for example a ground sensor to measure temperature, soil moisture and electrical conductivity, is as following (this is the current status of an installed sensor in the first “patio” in Córdoba):

ground sensor data model.txt

We can configure the subscription to send the more interesting attributes from the sensor to the app (probably you don't need the lorawan network parameters), for example id, type, dateObserved, refPatio, soilConductivity, soilMoisture and soilTemperature. The HTTP POST will include a JSON with the configured attributes, and it will be sent in real-time (very useful for you if you want to propose to users some missions or collect some data depending on the value of a specific parameter, for example the occupation level of the market).

For KPIs data exchange, we propose to use the standard data model of KPI fiware entities:

<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.KeyPerformanceIndicator/blob/master/KeyPerformanceIndicator/doc/spec.md>

KPIs definition
template

NOTE: We can get the value data from your API, and we can parse it to insert the KPI in the specific format allowed by de OCB.

THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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Wellness TechGroup

IN HABIT DATA PLATFORM

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Disclaimer: The content of this document does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union and in no way anticipates the European Commission's future policy in this area. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

INDEX

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Scope	3
3. How it works.....	3
4. Dashboard.....	4
5. API	4

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1. Introduction

IN-HABIT data platform is a FIWARE-based platform designed and created by WELLNESS TECH GROUP following the requirements of the IN HABIT PROJETC, an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to identify visionary and integrated solutions to promote inclusive health and wellbeing in small and medium-sized cities. The platform will collect information from several sources (devices, sensors, cameras, app...) and will show the information in a GRAFANA-based dashboard, and through API.

2. Scope

IN HABIT PLATFORM will collect data coming from different sources. Those sources could be used to help investigating how the mobilization of existing undervalued resources, such as culture and heritage, food, human-animal bonds, and art and environment, might contribute to boosting health and wellbeing, with a focus on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion.

To do that, information from different sources will be collected and analyzed to help getting those objectives to be done.

3. How it works

Data platform will collect information that will be provide from different sources, gather the information and public it on a dashboard.

The information collect will be from

- Sensors, installed on the cities, that will collect information about some weather variables and conditions
- Cameras, that will give data about people gather on specific places and times
- Devices, that will inform about how people use bins
- Book on a tree APP, in charge of collecting information from missions and task that people will complete on the cities.

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Data flow follows this network map.

Integration details will be described in another document

4. Dashboard

The information gathered from those sources will be gather, processed and showed on a GRAFANA-based dashboard, that will show the information in different levels

- Real time information gathers from devices, sensors, and app
- Graphics comparing different values and progression
- KPIs based on the information collected

5. API

The information gathered from those sources will be also available from and API, so it can be used for other purposes that will be defined in the IN-HABIT project

